

Synthesis of 1,4-Bis(5'-substituted-benzylidene-2'-phenyl/methyl-4'-imidazolinone-3'-ylamino)-phthalazine as Potential Anticonvulsant Agents

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HYDRAZINOPHTHALAZINES¹ are used as anti-hypertensive agents. The therapeutic importance of imidazolinones has been reported²⁻⁴. Sometimes the fusion of two heterocyclic nuclei enhances the biological profile many-fold than its parent nuclei. In continuation of our work on fused heterocycles of pharmacological interest, we have now synthesised the title compounds (1) bearing phthalazine and azlactone moieties in a single molecular framework and evaluated their anticonvulsant activity.

1

R = Aryl
X = H/Ph

The structures of the compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points of the compounds were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435-IR spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (200 MHz) on a Varian CFT-20 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel plates using benzene-acetone (9 : 1) solvent.

Acetyl benzoylglycine³, 4-substituted-benzylidene-2-methyl/phenyl-4-oxazolones³ and 1,4-bis-hydrazinophthalazine⁴ were prepared by reported methods.

1,4-Bis(5'-substituted-benzylidene-2'-phenyl/methyl-4'-imidazolinone-3'-ylamino)phthalazines (1): The oxazolones were heated with 1,4-bis-hydrazino phthalazine in an oil-bath at 140° for 1 h. The jelly-like mass obtained was recrystallised from methanol to yield the products (Table 1): ν_{\max} 3 020–3 100 (Ar-CH), 3 000–2 990 (C=C), 1 710 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N), 1 280 (C-O) and 1 180 cm^{-1} (C-N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.42 (6H, s), 2.6 (2H, m), 7.8–8.6 (14H, m) and 10.8 (2H, br).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1*

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C
	X=C₆H₅		
1.	3-Aminophenyl	C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₁₀ O ₂	180
2.	4-Aminophenyl	C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₁₀ O ₂	173
3.	2-Chlorophenyl	C ₄₀ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	140
4.	3-Chlorophenyl	C ₄₀ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	281
5.	4-Chlorophenyl	C ₄₀ H ₂₆ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	109
6.	Cinnamyl	C ₄₄ H ₃₂ N ₈ O ₂	130
7.	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	C ₄₀ H ₂₄ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₄	208
8.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	C ₄₀ H ₂₄ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₄	230
9.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₄₄ H ₃₆ N ₈ O ₆	145
10.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₄₀ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₄	195
11.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₄₀ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₄	130
12.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	C ₄₂ H ₃₂ N ₈ O ₆	170
13.	3-Methoxyphenyl	C ₄₂ H ₃₂ N ₈ O ₄	250d
14.	4-Methoxyphenyl	C ₄₂ H ₃₂ N ₈ O ₄	140
15.	2-Nitrophenyl	C ₄₀ H ₂₆ N ₁₀ O ₆	95
16.	3-Nitrophenyl	C ₄₀ H ₂₆ N ₁₀ O ₆	70
17.	Phenyl	C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₈ O ₂	180
18.	2-(1-Thienyl)	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂	135
	X=CH₃		
19.	3-Aminophenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₁₀ O ₂	200
20.	4-Aminophenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₁₀ O ₂	170
21.	2-Chlorophenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	280
22.	3-Chlorophenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	135
23.	4-Chlorophenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₂	152
24.	Cinnamyl	C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₂	125
25.	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₄	180
26.	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₂ Cl ₄	165
27.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₈ O ₆	240
28.	3-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₈ O ₄	150
29.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₈ O ₄	280
30.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	C ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₆	200
31.	3-Methoxyphenyl	C ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₄	230
32.	4-Methoxyphenyl	C ₃₂ H ₂₈ N ₈ O ₄	140
33.	2-Nitrophenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₆	270
34.	3-Nitrophenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₁₀ O ₆	185
35.	Phenyl	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₈ O ₂	145
36.	2-(1-Thienyl)	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₂ S ₂	180
37.	Phenobarbitone (reference drug)	—	—

*Yield=50–70% ; C, H and N values are satisfactory.

Anticonvulsant activity: Out of 36 compounds (Table 1), 25 compounds were screened for their anticonvulsant activity. The activity was determined against pentylenetetrazole induced seizures⁵ in albino mice (25–30 g) at 100 mg/kg i.p. dose level compared to 100% activity of phenobarbitone (a

reference drug). The compounds were suspended in 5% aqueous gum acacia to give a concentration of 25% (w/v). Four hours after administration of compounds, the mice were injected with pentylene tetrazol (PNT) at 100 mg/kg and observed for 60 min for occurrence of seizures. Clonic spasm persisting for atleast 5 s was considered to be a threshold convulsion and transient intermittent jerk and tremor were disregarded. Animal not exhibiting threshold convulsion during 60 min were considered protected. The numbers protected in each group of mice was recorded and the anticonvulsant activity of the compounds was represented in terms of % protection. The mice were further observed for 24 h for recording mortality.

Marked anticonvulsant activity was shown by compounds sl. nos. 6, 10, 15, 16, 23, 24, 28, 31, 33 and 34 (70–80% protection) and moderate activity by compounds nos. 2, 4, 5, 7, 14, 17, 22, 32 and 35 (40–60%). These observations also indicate that the presence of NO₂ and OCH₃ groups increases biological activity.

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